

Project Summary

Overview

This proposal aims to rapidly advance expert stakeholder recommendations that emerged from the NSF supported *April 2nd Workshop Exploring National Infrastructure for Public Access Usage and Impact Reporting*. In 12 months, this EAGER aims to a) document the usage and impact data supply chain for article and data research outputs, to complement findings for books, and b) engage research infrastructure stakeholders to crosswalk usage and impact related vocabularies across scholarship outputs and disciplines.

The usage and impact data pertaining to a single publicly-accessible research output (book, article, or dataset) are created across a complex array of public and private publishers, publication distributors and aggregators, repositories, discovery services and service platforms. Comparable, high-quality information access is vital to research information management systems, impact reporting, and innovation policy; and is inherent to the provision of scholarship impact statements alongside data management plans. Yet, compiling usage and impact metrics for publicly-accessible scholarship across public and private repositories, services, and publishers is a time and data-science intensive activity undertaken by individual researchers, universities, libraries, and publishers. While services provision some usage data, challenges related to secure data brokerage, automated data access, and auditing by a trusted, neutral infrastructure complicate the exchange and aggregation of usage data across commercial and non-commercial competitors. This proposal aims to inform whether a national cyberinfrastructure is needed to support the exchange and processing of sensitive and proprietary usage and impact metrics generated by US-based research publishers and distributors.

Intellectual Merit

This work advances America's National Strategy to Advance Privacy-Preserving Data Sharing and Analytics Strategic Priorities 3, 4, and 5. It is transformative as it explores domestic applicability of European industry data space (IDS) standards and mechanisms to audit and control sensitive data exchange and processing across public and industrial partners. It has the potential to upend status quo reliance on data lakes and repositories for usage and impact metric publication, access, and reuse. This translational research is high risk as it engages diverse stakeholders across disciplines and entrenched sustainability models to co-develop applied vocabularies and frameworks that would support the pilot application of European data regulatory frameworks in the US context where the disruptive IDS technological approach to data sharing governance on the distributed web is unproven.

Broader Impacts

In line with NSF's new research security aims, this project will inform infrastructure development to ensure the integrity of evidence-based decision-making related to US research funding impact, specifically by fostering a multi-disciplinary community of public and private stakeholders to develop and crosswalk vocabulary related to data provenance and security, processing algorithm transparency, and risk-mitigation associated with sensitive usage data reappropriation. This EAGER would jumpstart US-infrastructure research to improve trusted data exchange by documenting the data supply chain for usage and impact metric data for publicly accessible journals and datasets, noting key differences from already documented usage data supply networks for books and monographs. This work would surface potential socio-technical challenges to adopting the European IDS model in the US context, which holds potential to inform both the developing OAEUDT and the European data space for research metrics.